

Curtin University

Curtin Open Knowledge Initiative

CAUL/CONZUL Institutional Dashboard Feedback Report

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CAUL/CONZUL Institutional Dashboard Feedback Report

In 2019, the Curtin Open Knowledge Initiative (COKI) developed a dashboard providing institutional summary data relating to open access for research output, publishers, journals, funders; research collaboration; altmetric events data; and staff gender diversity data for universities in Aotearoa/New Zealand and Australia. The dashboard was launched to CAUL (Council of Australian University Librarians) and CONZUL (Council of New Zealand University Librarians) in October 2019. In March 2020, COKI launched a research project to evaluate the dashboard data, structure and interface. We invited members of CAUL and CONZUL to register to view the dashboard data for their individual institutions, and then to participate in an online survey with follow up telephone interview in order to provide feedback on the data and the dashboard functionality.

Methodology

We developed an online survey using Qualtrics software and invited CAUL and CONZUL members via email to register to access the dashboard, review their institution's data, and to participate in the anonymous survey. The final survey question offered participants the option to expand on their responses in a follow up telephone interview. Curtin University Human Research Ethics Committee (HREC) approved this study (HRE2020-0086). The survey and interviews took place during March and April 2020 as the COVID-19 virus expanded worldwide, disrupting working conditions and activities of all Aotearoa/New Zealand and Australia universities and staff. This affected people's time and priorities and had some impact on the extent of survey responses. The two-step process that involved first registering and then completing the survey may have also affected the number of responses.

Additional information emerging from follow up emails, questions and comments from some registrants and survey participants is incorporated into this report. Responses from the telephone interviews and the emails are anonymised.

We received seventeen responses to the online survey: ten fully completed, four partially completed and three minimally completed. We conducted two follow up telephone interviews. The outcomes of the survey and interviews are summarised below. Tabulated detail from the survey is in Appendix I and transcripts of the telephone interviews are in Appendix II.

Summary of outcomes

The majority of respondents work in libraries, managing institutional repositories and providing research services or support. Some are in middle management positions

with one identifying as Library management. One respondent works in a Research Office. Responses indicate that in addition to library staff, the dashboard data are of interest to Research Office personnel and staff in Faculties and Schools. Respondents are very interested in the benchmarking data from other institutions in their countries in order to compare performances, particularly in open access output and staff diversity.

Overall the response to the dashboard product and the data provided is very positive. Based on the survey responses, telephone interviews, email and other comments, key areas of the dashboard to review are as follows:

1. For the 'Situating with other universities' graph, include more detail in benchmarking data, enable zoom in for more detail, make more prominent, increase the size.
2. Extend 'Situating with other universities' and other two graphs to include NZ universities.
3. Include other universities' open access and diversity data to enable comparisons.
4. Extend granularity of some open access data, e.g. disciplinary analysis, FOR codes.
5. Funder publications - citations for non-open access compliant papers.
6. Provide open access status for Altmetric events data.
7. Link Collaboration and open access data of institutional papers, e.g., analyse open access output by Australian grouping or international co-authorship.
8. Clearer labelling text for donut graphs.
9. Improve colour/contrast of map graphs.
10. Standardise table and graph heading positioning.
11. Check data display is available for each institution.
12. Incorporate Documentation and Help/Contacts directly into the dashboard interface.
13. Develop institutional logins.

Response detail

University groupings and work roles

Respondents who completed the survey work in universities from the following groupings: Australian Technology Network, Group of Eight, Regional Universities Network, Unaligned Australian Universities and New Zealand Universities. There may be multiple respondents from the same institution.

Follow up telephone interview participants are from Unaligned Australian Universities and the Regional Universities Network groups.

Respondents work in the following areas within their institutions: Library management, Institutional repositories, Library research services or support, Library Systems, Scholarly communication, Research/Planning/Strategy Office.

Two respondents who did not complete the survey indicated they had not had time to explore the dashboard.

The dashboard interface and data

The majority of participants indicates the dashboard *gives a new perspective to existing data and provides new data.*

Interview comments are enthusiastic:

- *Found it overall good and useful, especially the visualisation. Like the interactivity.*
- *...it's very comprehensive.*
- *The dashboard data complements our IR reporting mechanisms...Very useful to have all the data together in one place and presented visually.*
- *This is a GREAT PRODUCT and thank you to everyone at Curtin.*

Data elements

The respondents found the following data elements useful/relevant to their work, in descending order:

- Institutional summary, Publications and their Open Access Status over time;
- OA Articles / Citations / Average Citations, Publisher venues;
- Geographical Breakdown of Collaborations, Open Access Per Funder, Diversity;
- Top 50 Funder Outputs / OA Count / % Not OA, Altmetrics.

Interview and survey comments on the data elements include:

- **OA/non-OA data** relating to changes over time, exponential curve very useful.
- **Citation data OA/non-OA**, averages collated visually in this way very useful for showing OA reluctant researchers the benefit of OA in terms of citations
- **The ARC/NHMRC compliance data** is very interesting, especially to some Senior Executives concerned about possible audit.
- **Funder data OA/non-OA** useful, especially for ARC, NHMRC. Researchers at the university publish in high quality journals at the behest of the university rather than OA journals. Library staff contact PIs at the end of a project/after publication and encourage green AAM deposit in IR, remind them of the ARC, NHMRC mandates, point them to the ARC, NHMRC OA policy pages. There is a lack of awareness re mandates but when PIs are reminded, they are happy to comply. "Compliance" is a "magic" word that works well.
- *It would be more useful if we could drill down into the data to see the details, e.g. for **funder publications** what are the citations for the non-OA compliant papers.*
- *Some of the data didn't seem to be linked to OA status, e.g. **altmetrics data** is interesting but unsure if OA influences altmetrics.*
- *The **Citations table** is very useful as data for OA/not OA citations is not easily available.*

- **Diversity** is interesting - would be useful to compare with the university's own data.

The graph **Situating with other Australian Institutions** is of great interest in terms of benchmarking with other institutions:

- *Benchmarking tables...were quite useful to see how we were tracking against other universities*
- *'Situating with other universities' graph is very useful as benchmarking data. Good to see how your own institution is tracking with others.*
- *Would be good to include NZ universities.*

Telephone interviewees commented on data elements they may not be familiar with:

- *Not anything unfamiliar with but the data are presented differently, e.g. **Journals OA data**. Reports like these are difficult to get from the IR (DSpace), and cannot get visualisations like these.*
- ***Journal and publisher** information will be of interest to some schools/faculties.*
- ***Diversity data**. Interesting to see the percentage of women on staff. Would be interested to see other universities' percentages to compare.*

Wish list

Survey and interview comments suggest further data elements that respondents would find useful, and some missing data:

- *Would be helpful if '**Situating with other institutions' graphs** included the NZ universities.*
- *Inclusion of the NZ Universities in the other two graphs could be considered.*
- ***Diversity** info is currently blank so not helpful, would be interesting if a reliable data source can be used, if not then would remove.*
- *Would like more granularity of data, e.g., more detail of how open access is achieved, types of output, **OA/Not OA publishing by disciplines (perhaps by FOR Codes)***
- *More **benchmarking**. Underlying data provided*
- *Discipline analysis of **citations** would be interesting.*
- *Currently **publishers / funders** have multiple entries e.g.: Wiley and Marsden. Aggregating these would give a more accurate picture - could remedy by downloading and collating, I guess.*
- *Drill down into the data to see the details, e.g. for **funder publications**, citations for **non-OA** compliant papers*
- *Collaboration - percentage of papers that are OA that have co-authors with Go8s or international co-authorship*
- *Cost of APCs.*

Updating data

The majority of online survey respondents indicated they would like to see the data updated every 6 months, followed by 12 months.

Sharing data

Participants indicate the data and dashboard will be useful to share with other library colleagues, managers, Research Office staff, school and faculty staff.

Telephone interviewees comments on sharing the dashboard and data:

- *Have already shown around library staff (made and circulated PDF copy). Will share with the Research Office, especially in relation to the [institution's] OA policy development.*
- *Shared with library colleagues who think it is amazing. Director, Research had been referred to it from a previous institution, and also thought it was amazing.*
- *Will share journal and publication data with schools and faculties. Will be useful in informing authors of the green, self-archiving options. Currently academics are required to self-archive in IR but need greater awareness of value.*

Several dashboard registrants asked via email if and how they could share the data with colleagues.

Layout, navigation and interface

Respondents find the layout and interface easy to use, selecting the following options in descending order:

- *Easy to navigate*
- *Very easy to navigate*
- *Somewhat easy to navigate*

Respondents made the following suggestions regarding labelling and colour contrasts for some graphs and tables:

- *Some simple **visual formatting** could help with navigation e.g.: headings in tables either centred over relevant columns or left justified (rather than to the right).*
- *In the '**Geographical Breakdown of Collaborations**' section the colours are quite pale and it would be good to have the name of the institution rather than the GRID in the hover over [referring to the map].*
- *Clearer labelling and definitions will be useful, e.g. the **OA donut wheel labels True/False** need to be clearer, i.e. **OA/not OA**.*
- *'**Situating with other institutions**' graph labels such as **percent_green**, **percent_gold** need to be clearer, especially for people who may not be so familiar and have not read the accompanying instruction sheet.*
- *Increase the size of the **benchmarking tables**; they were quite useful to see how we were tracking against other universities.*

Download formats

Respondents found the following download formats for graphs most useful, in descending order:

- *Download CSV*
- *Export to sheets and Explore*

One respondent commented on the PDF download of the whole report:

There is no way to view all the data. I can't hover over the images to get actual figures. It only generates the first rows on the tables, thus missing some of the year range.

Documentation

The survey responses indicate the parts of the documentation about the dashboard they find most helpful are:

- *Methodology, Definitions of open access status*
- *Explanation of graphics*
- *Funder analysis, Australia/NZ dashboard technical details*

And added the following comments:

- *Methodology explanation in the accompanying documentation is very useful.*
- *Wasn't especially clear where to find this documentation although I'm sure it would be very helpful.*

Access mechanisms

Access to the dashboard is currently by individual registration. Several survey participants and dashboard registrants expressed interest in an institutional login. Others asked if they could share their logins with colleagues. For example, one email comment asked:

...if there is only one login per institute for COKI or if numerous staff from the same institute can have their own individual login.

In summary

The CAUL/CONZUL survey respondents appear to be impressed with the scope of the data and the dashboard product. Their comments, suggestions and interest in the open access and benchmarking data, as well as the dashboard visualisation and interactivity, suggest the product is filling a gap, providing relevant and valuable information that is unavailable or not easily obtained elsewhere. The number of survey responses is small, but they provide a rich source of data that will enable COKI to expand and enhance the product further.

Appendix I: Tabulated online survey responses

Q2. Which group is your university a member of?

Australian Technology Network (ATN)	3
Group of Eight (Go8)	3
Innovative Research Universities (IRU)	0
Regional Universities Network (RUN)	1
Unaligned Australian universities	2
New Zealand Universities	5

Q3. In which area do you work at your university?

Repositories	5
Library research services/support	4
Library systems	0
Data services	0
Scholarly communication	1
Library Copyright/policy	0
Library Information services	0
Research/planning/strategy office	1
Other	3

Comments:

Responsible for a range of Library services including research services, IR, systems areas; Library Systems and Repositories; Library management.

Q 3. Have you interacted with the COKI dashboard data for your university?

Yes	14
No	3

Q4. If you have not interacted with the dashboard data please indicate why.

I have not had time to explore the dashboard	2
Other reasons	1 *

*No text available

Q5. How does the dashboard data extend your understanding of your university's open knowledge performance?

Provides new data	5
Gives a new perspective to existing data	7
Does not extend understanding	0
Other comments	2 *

*No text available

Q6. Which data elements are useful/relevant to your work?

Institutional summary	7
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Publications and their Open Access Status over time	7
OA Articles / Citations / Average Citations	6
Geographical Breakdown of Collaborations	3
Top 50 Funder Outputs / OA Count / % Not OA	3
Open Access Per Funder	4
Funder Acknowledgements	0
Diversity	2
Publisher venues	5
Altmetrics	1
Types of output	0
All of the above	2
What other data would be useful?	1 *

*No text available

Q7. How frequently does the data need to be updated to maximise its usefulness?

Monthly	2
6 months	4
12 months	3
Other	2

Other: 3 months

Q8. Which download formats do you find most useful?

Download CSV	8
Export to sheets	2
Explore	2
None of the above	1
Other suggestions?	1 *

*No text available

Q9. How clear is the layout, navigation of the dashboard?

Somewhat easy to navigate	2
Easy to navigate	5
Very easy to navigate	4
Not easy to navigate	0

Q10. Which parts of the documentation about the dashboard provided to you are helpful?

Methodology	4
Definitions of open access status	4
Funder analysis	1
Explanation of graphics, p. 4	2
Australia/NZ dashboard technical details	1
All of the above	2
Further comments?	2

Comments:

Wasn't especially clear where to find this documentation although I'm sure it would be very helpful.

Q11. What additional suggestions do you have to improve the dashboard for the Australia/Aotearoa New Zealand university communities?

Diversity info is currently blank so not helpful, would be interesting if a reliable data source can be used, if not then would remove [Note: Sources are provided in the documentation. It is not clear why data did not display]. Some simple visual formatting could help with navigation e.g.: headings in tables either centred over relevant columns or left justified (rather than to the right). Currently publishers /funders have multiple entries e.g. Wiley, Marsden. Aggregating these would give a more accurate picture - could remedy by downloading and collating, I guess. Would be helpful to be able to compare with other institutions' dashboards and see these.

As a staff member of a NZ university it would be good to have a comparison with the other NZ universities. Being able to zoom in on the Situating with other universities graph.

Interactive (highlight certain points). More benchmarking. Underlying data provided.

The 'Situating with other Australian Institutions' would be helpful if it included the NZ universities. A hover over feature for the data points in the top graphic would be good. Inclusion of the NZ Universities in the other two graphs could be considered. In the 'Geographical Breakdown of Collaborations' section the colours are quite pale and it would be good to have the name of the institution rather than the GRID in the hover over.

To increase the size of the benchmarking tables; they were quite useful to see how we were tracking against other universities.

At this stage we haven't had an opportunity to review the dashboard.

No comment

All good.

Nothing this stage - looks good!

It would be more useful if we could drill down into the data to see the details, e.g. for funder publications what are the citations for the non-OA compliant papers? Documentation should be included on the dashboard somewhere (sorry if it is and I just can't find it). Some of the data didn't seem to be linked to OA status, e.g. altmetrics data is interesting but unsure if OA influences altmetrics.

Appendix II: Transcripts of telephone interviews

The Curtin University's Human Research Ethics Committee approval required that respondents contact the researcher to arrange a follow up interview, with contact details included in the survey final thank you message. Two respondents made contact. The follow up telephone interviews were transcribed manually. Five other survey respondents indicated they would take part in an interview but did not make contact. As the online survey respondents are anonymous it was not possible to contact them directly.

Interview: 12 March 2020

Q1. Which group is your university a member of?

A: *Unaligned.*

Q2. Does your university have an open access policy or mandate for your institution's research output?

A: *In development, hope to be in place by the end of the year. Mirrors the QUT policy with its mandate that contributes to a high level of IR deposit. Universities Australia and CAUL are pushing for OA policies to support CoalitionS/PlanS.*

Q3. Which data elements in the dashboard are useful/not useful for you? Can you expand on the reasons?

A:

- *The 'Situating with other universities' graph is very useful as benchmarking data. Good to see how your own institution is tracking with others.*
- *The display of the dashboard is easy to show others in the university such as the Research Office, library management.*
- *OA/non-OA data relating to changes over time, exponential curve very useful.*
- *Citation data OA/non-OA, averages collated visually in this way very useful for showing OA reluctant researchers the benefit of OA in terms of citations*
- *Methodology explanation in the accompanying documentation is very useful.*
- *The dashboard data complements our IR reporting mechanisms*
- *Funder data OA/non-OA useful, especially for ARC, NHMRC. Researchers at the university publish in high quality journals at the behest of the university rather than OA journals. Library staff contact PIs at the end of a project/after publication and encourage green AAM deposit in IR, remind them of the ARC, NHMRC mandates, point them to the ARC, NHMRC OA policy pages. There is a lack of awareness re mandates but when PIs are reminded, they are happy to comply. "Compliance" is a "magic" word that works well.*

Q4. Which data elements were you not familiar with?

A: *Diversity data. Interesting to see the percentage of women on staff. Do the figures just relate to OA publications? Would be interested to see other universities'*

percentages to compare.

Q5. In which area do you work?

A: Manager, Research Services, includes the IR, OA, scholarly publishing, RDM and metrics. Works with and supports staff on other campuses.

Q6. Have you referred or do you plan to refer anyone else in your university to the data on the dashboard? Which data and which areas in your institution?

A: Have already shown around library staff (made and circulated PDF copy). Will share with the Research Office, especially in relation to the OA policy development. Very useful to have all the data together in one place and presented visually.

Q7. Which other data elements relating to open knowledge performance do you think would be useful for your work area and other parts of your university?

A: Can't really think of any.

Q8. What further thoughts do you have about the data and the dashboard?

A:

- Very easy to scroll through.*
- Suggest making the graph 'Situating with other universities' more prominent as it is useful benchmarking data.*

This is a GREAT PRODUCT and thank you to everyone at Curtin.

Interview 2: 1 April 2020

Q1. Which group is your university a member of?

A: Regional Universities Network (RUN). Also, AOASG, Queensland University Libraries Office of Cooperation (QULOC).

Q2. Does your university have an open access policy or mandate for your institution's research output?

A: Have had policy for 5 years, recommending author self-archiving in IR. University is not a Category 1 Research funding institution (HERDC) so limited funds to support APCs. Policy is being revised.

Q3. Which data elements in the dashboard are useful/not useful for you? Can you expand on the reasons?

A: Discussed with the university's Library group who meet to discuss open scholarship. Found it overall good and useful, especially the visualisation. Like the

interactivity. Would like more granularity of data, e.g., more detail of how open access achieved, types of output.

Interested in the OA performances of other universities in Australia beyond the Situating with other universities graphs. The Citations table is very useful as data for OA/not OA citations is not easily available. Discipline analysis of citations would be interesting.

Diversity is interesting - would be useful to compare with the university's own data.

Q4. Which data elements were you not familiar with?

A: Not anything unfamiliar with but the data are presented differently, e.g. Journals OA data. Reports like these are difficult to get from the IR (DSpace), and cannot get visualisations like these. Journal and publisher information will be of interest to some schools/faculties.

Q5. In which area do you work?

A: Research support, Library. Includes outreach to schools, faculties, senior executives, HDRs, ECRs about the IR, ERA, best practice publishing. Getting feedback regarding the library's services.

Q6. Have you referred or do you plan to refer anyone else in your university to the data on the dashboard? Which data and which areas in your institution?

A: Shared with library colleagues who think it is amazing. Director, Research had been referred to it from a previous institution, and also thought it was amazing.

Will share journal and publication data with schools and faculties. Will be useful in informing authors of the green, self-archiving options. Currently academics are required to self-archive in IR but need greater awareness of value. Research Office is looking at a new research management system that will integrate with IR.

Questions I imagine will be asked by individual academics and the Faculties will be along the lines of discipline breakdown, cost of APCs, and percentage of papers that are OA that have co-authors with G08s or international co-authorship.

Q7. Which other data elements relating to open knowledge performance do you think would be useful for your work area and other parts of your university?

A: Granularity of data as mentioned above. But it's very comprehensive.

Q8. What further thoughts do you have about the data and the dashboard?

A: Clearer labelling and definitions will be useful, e.g. the OA donut wheel labels True/False need to be clearer, OA, not OA. 'Situating with other institutions' graph labels such as percent_green, percent_gold need to be clearer, especially for people who may not be so familiar and have not read the accompanying instruction sheet.

For the PDF download there is no way to view all the data. For example, I can't hover over the images to get the actual figures. It also only generates the first rows on the tables, thus missing some of the year range.

How often will it be updated? Have you also considered using Dimensions, lens.org? I had already seen the COKI presentation at CAUL webinar from May 2019 and was aware of the project.

The ARC/NHMRC compliance data is very interesting, especially to some Senior Executives, concerned about possible audit. Have ARC/NHMRC seen this data?

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